

GURDJIEFF & OUSPENSKY

EUROCENTRICISM AND VEDANTA

A paper which examines western errors in understanding Vedanta

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IMPORTANT NOTE

Due to the fact that many concepts within the Vedanta philosophy do not have suitable or appropriate words in European languages, many Sanskrit words have no direct English equivalent, hence they need to be kept (in *bold italic*) in the text and their meanings need to be learned by readers. Please use the glossary on page 32 for this purpose.

SECTION ONE - THE UK SCHOOLS

Introduction

Advaita Vedanta is the philosophy which has grown out of a timeless and ancient system called *Sanatana Dharma* or "The Ancient System of Righteousness". It has been preserved for modern times in the Indian subcontinent by the tradition of the teachers who follow the system set up by the great Indian holy philosopher Adi Shankara (the *Śaṅkarāchāryas*).

The central plank of Advaita Vedanta aims to assist each individual to discover what their True Self or individual soul is, and how it relates to the purpose of human life in discovering the Creator of all things. G.I.Gurdjieff and P.D.Ouspensky were Russian philosophers who were thought to have been interested in this concept; they brought a system for approaching the study of psychology to western Europe in the early part of the 20th century. Both these men had a significant effect on the way many European and UK philosophy schools understood the subject of self-discovery. Yet there were fundamental flaws in their approach.

In my youth, 57 or so years ago, I took a deep interest in the practical aspects of the Vedanta philosophy of India. To further this interest I studied at various UK schools who were also interested in practical philosophy. At that time I was not so fully aware of the phenomenon which I have recently called Eurocentricism (see the paper on "Did Jesus Study Vedanta?")¹. Vedanta has appeared in Europe in various forms over several centuries, but it was a London school of philosophy which made a direct connection to the ancient tradition of Vedanta through the *Śaṅkarāchārya* system. This connection came about when a character called Mahesh (Maharishi) toured the world spreading a meditation system which he himself devised. Maharishi was also connected to the same Vedanta system in India and through him a connection was made.

Hence this paper has an autobiographical content; but it is produced here as a guide to those in Europe (and maybe worldwide) who would wish to make a useful connection with Advaita Vedanta but would like to avoid the mistakes made by the UK schools and to also eliminate the effects of Eurocentricism when putting the system to practice.

There is no intention here to put down those who have made mistakes in understanding Vedanta. It is quite understandable that Europeans have some difficulty in understanding cultures from the East. This difficulty is minimised if prior to the study, the effects of Eurocentricism are understood first and eliminated as best as can be.

¹ Read this paper to find out my view of what Eurocentricism is.

To avoid using actual names I will use acronyms derived from the names of those people and organisations who need to be examined here. We will see examples of the mistakes which can be made when a practical study of Vedanta is undertaken and is marred by Eurocentricism.

This paper has been adapted from the content of two appendices in the book "The Life and Teachings of His Divinity Shri Guru Deva" which was published in 2014. ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0.

I begin the paper describing the history and the involvement of both G.I.Gurdjieff and P.D.Ouspensky in bringing their philosophy to western Europe and to London UK and how Eurocentricism affected this.

Beginnings of the UK London School SSNP

A group called SSNP stemmed from investigations started by the Russian G.I.Gurdjieff at the end of the 19th century and first part of the 20th. His pupil, the Russian journalist P.D.Ouspensky, came to the UK between the 1st and 2nd world wars, and began an organisation which was seeking to get to the bottom of what G.I.Gurdjieff was teaching. This teaching was essentially a mixture of Persian Sufism and other teachings derived from the East, centuries before his time. The teachings were mixed with various indigenous traditions which survived in the Afghanistan / Hindu Kush areas and also in Turkey and surrounding countries. Contrary to the belief of UK philosophy school leaders, some of the ideas of Gurdjieff were his own. Also they never were, in previous history, part of the Advaita Vedanta tradition as the UK philosophy schools thought.

After studying and practising aspects of various teachings in different locations in the middle east and central Asia, Gurdjieff became a self styled *guru* character in Russia. He deemed himself suitable to teach others about "remembering the self" before he really understood what it was to do that. Ouspensky finally concluded that he and Gurdjieff only had fragments of a teaching about the inner life of man, yet himself still deemed that he was in a position to teach others a method or "system". This is how, in past centuries, the various versions of the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition in India have become corrupted into other systems. People who do not fully know, convincing others that they do know. This is a universal trait of human beings, currently prevalent in the USA. Shri Ramakrishna rebuked a learned enquirer,

"That's the one hobby of you Calcutta people - giving lectures and bringing other people into the light! Who are you to teach others?" (i.e. when you have not really understood the purpose and practice of the philosophy).

Echoing Jesus' example of "removing the beam from the eye" first before trying to teach others (i.e. removing their mote).

Gurdjieff convinced many people that he had, not only esoteric teaching which was previously secret, but that he also had mystic powers. It may or may not be true that he possessed these things, but his own approach and personality (ego) were the main stumbling blocks; in this way he did not realise that the teachings which he had studied had as their goal, renunciation of the worldly life and a total focus on the existing unchanging purity of the human soul, requiring sublimation of the ego. However, eventually Gurdjieff's teaching was unable to accept that there was an existing, immortal, pure essence dwelling within all human beings. A matter which is at the heart of Vedanta. So his system was missing a vital concept from the outset.

There is no doubt that Gurdjieff had awoken a deep curiosity in Ouspensky; after which Ouspensky devoted his life to seeking success with the methods and practices which he had been taught; all relating to how a "permanent centre" in a person could be created. Ouspensky saw, what were to him, obvious misunderstandings or misapplications by Gurdjieff in the teachings he had received. This led Ouspensky to break from Gurdjieff and start up his own group. This he eventually did in West London; the SSNP.

Ouspensky was a brilliant writer. He has written on very profound subjects. His original interests were connected with how human civilisations made use of philosophy, science, art and religion and how these subjects interacted with each other in leading mankind towards a better life. He was also interested in an inner development of the human being. But he did not seek a competent and true teacher which might have helped him in his quest. Hence, he was not able to discover what inner development might mean in practice. Near the end of his life Ouspensky came to realise that he had not approached the subject, which he called "self remembering" in the right way. He really wanted his followers to scrap his system and start again. But sensing that this would leave them rudderless they were unable to do that, entirely. Eventually, near to his passing away in 1947, he asked his close follower Dr. F.C.R to carry on the search for the correct or complete teaching. This ultimately led to the connection of SSNP with India and the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition, and a true teacher known as His Holiness Shantanand Saraswati, who had been the disciple of the Divine person known as Shri Guru Deva. See the aforementioned book ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0.

The people at SSNP, who followed on from Ouspensky, sought to bring about corrections to the previous mistakes, but they did not change the teaching model which had been set up. This model involved an institutional approach, with some people who were supposed to be knowers and others who were learners and a single person at the top. The learners were expected to comply with rules or conditions set out by the one at the top and regulated by the knowers. Groups are formed of spiritually unwise people sitting in front of another spiritually unwise person, from whom they are supposed receive guidance. Thus it would seem SSNP simply repeated the same European model which started with the Holy Roman Empire (Catholic church). That whereby, people who may be spiritually ignorant, set themselves up as being the ones closer to God (or their equivalent of Him), and were to be respected by the others through a system of domination of their thought processes, now called Eurocentricism. This European idea made belief systems into a semi-political subject; the systematic control of a large number of people. This is different from the Vedanta approach, which seeks only to give guidance to those who want it. The Eurocentric approach seeks to control the people through rules and regulations; imposing the same obligations on all. This is a possible recipe for eventual failure, in the sense of achieving the final spiritual goal for any individual, due to the one-size-fits-all approach. Many UK philosophy schools use this model.

But readers should not make the European mistake of supplanting in their minds the phrase "**spiritually ignorant**" with any word or phrase which conveys the idea of "**evil**". None of the people in any of the UK schools can ever be called evil. They are mostly good people who seek truthfulness, goodness and high moral standards. It is the narrowness of the thinking which attracts the term "**ignorant**", when their control of people goes off the straight track. The people are OK, it is the system or the ideas of central control (Eurocentricism) which are off track. The one-size-fits-all approach.

The word "ignorance" has two main parts to it. The central part is "gno" which is connected with knowing or with knowledge (gnosis). The "i" at the beginning gives the word the sense of "I know", which indicates a personal claim on knowledge. This word was coined for the English language to denote this narrow approach to knowledge. Generally it is thought that 'ignorance' means lacking knowledge, but its true or original meaning is the misuse of knowledge. In one of the *upanisads* of the Advaita Vedanta tradition there is a verse; "**He who claims to know, knows nothing. He who claims nothing, knows.**" It is in this sense I am

using the term "spiritually ignorant". There is no intention to convey that such people are anything other than commonly decent people, trying in their own way to apply what they believe will lead to knowing their own True Self. They are simply using the wrong ideas to achieve this.

The SSNP was on the Great Western Road in London UK, and it was the main location where most of their activities and meetings took place. As numbers grew and their locations were more widespread, meetings were arranged in the houses of group takers. When I joined in 1974, I was living in Sutton in Surrey UK, the group I attended was in Reigate in Surrey. Although I often went to the London headquarters which was not so far away from where I lived at the time.

Here I will explain more about the connection which the SSNP had with my own studies and with the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition. The purpose here is to clarify some of the western difficulties in understanding the philosophy and culture of the East. These difficulties became clearer and clearer to me during my membership of SSNP.

Another purpose here is to draw up some of the differences between the true *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition and the way that western organisations apply it. Many of the characteristics and approaches discussed here also apply to other UK schools which have connections and similarities with the SSNP; such as SES philosophy section and the SoM who teach meditation. Both these schools have also taken teaching from His Holiness Shantanand Saraswati and are now worldwide organisations. All these three organisations have made mistakes associated with Gurdjieff's own ideas of what the spiritual subject is. These ideas stem from the false conceptions common to all people. The SES philosophy section sprung originally from SSNP.

The mention of the word "mistakes" will immediately alert some readers to think that I have sentiments which may be anti UK-school. Let me say from the outset, that such an idea would be improper. I knew Dr. FCR very well. I often had one to one talks with him in his room in the London headquarters after the large Tuesday meetings. From things which he said, I can say with confidence that towards the end of his tenure at the SSNP, he had begun to see that there was a far greater difference between the Ouspensky "system" and Advaita Vedanta than he had at first thought. He also knew that the SSNP was firmly stuck in the mud of the Ouspensky "system" and that it would not be himself that would be pulling them out, as it was a bigger job than he had the time and energy for. But he seemed not to be aware of Eurocentricism or its effect.

I also knew the leader of SES (L.M.) quite well. I played chess with him at Stanhill Court country retreat in Surrey. There I had chance to observe him closely without the interruption of words coming from his lips. Few have had this opportunity. I have great respect for what it was that both these men (Dr.FCR and LM) were trying to do. However, very few people would applaud the actions of a gardener who attempted to cut a large grass lawn with a pair of scissors. He might get there in the end, but we all know it is not the appropriate tool for the job. To clarify this a little see if you can connect with the following two analogies.

I was trained and qualified in the structural engineering profession and in a position to teach several young men to become proficient and qualified engineers in respect of all aspects of building construction. This however, did not give me the right to claim to be a teacher of architecture, whatever similarities these two professions have by being connected to design in building construction. A ripe golden quince may resemble a pear in appearance, but they are not the same thing.

We will see later on that the word "mistake" used above is appropriate in respect of its meaning "to *take* the wrong one". But to sum up as a prelude to what will come, I will simply state here that unknown to Dr.FCR at the time, he had gone through a process which we can liken to the game "Chinese whispers". This came about because he heard a word translated from Russian into the English word "self". Many decades later he heard another word translated from Sanskrit into the English word "self". The mistake was that he took these to be the same meaning. They most certainly were not.

There is no intention here to say that any UK school should not be teaching Advaita Vedanta. The *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition is clear that all are entitled to study and teach the philosophy in whatever way they wish. There is however, a vast difference between the traditional teaching of Advaita Vedanta, which requires a chain of Self-realised souls as teachers, and that which is the approach of any of these UK schools, where there are no Self-realised teachers. This difference lies in the method whereby Self-realisation is generally reached after a person becomes the close follower (disciple) of a Self-realised soul. Hence, UK schools should try to comprehend, from the following text, their true position in relation to the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition and not make claims in relation to the transmission of teaching related to Self-realisation, untrue to that tradition. There is no error in simply teaching the philosophy. Truthfulness lost will lead to disintegration in a world which needs truth.

It is part of the *Śaṅkarāchārya* and the Advaita Vedanta traditions that the mind is exposed to repeated reading of certain information so that it can be properly impressed on the reader's mind. This concept is in some way utilised here. Therefore readers will find certain facts are intentionally repeated within different contexts, for the above reason.

To close this introduction here is my view of how this, and what follows, fit into the overall aims of Advaita Vedanta philosophy.

All Self-realised souls know on reaching that exalted state, that life in this world is comparable to the dreams we have in the night time. This means that in the waking state, as in the dream, we are truly convinced that all is real and is happening to us as we perceive it. Whereas the truth of the situation is, that our experience in the world with our body and senses, is as impermanent and unreliable as those events of our dreams. From the false conceptions imposed through the universal illusion called *maya*, we assume that all we see and experience is immutable and will always remain the same. HH Swami Satyananda Maharaj said :-

"You see, even the body changes, doctors say. Every cell changes every day. You go yesterday to the Yamuna river, today you go back that stream has gone. Still we say Yamuna. It is all changing, everything is changing. There is only one entity which does not change; That is our real existence (i.e. the True Self)." ²

This illusion is also called *līlā*, meaning sport or playtime. Advaita Vedanta also uses this concept as a way of explaining the otherwise difficult subject of the difference between, how ordinary people see the world and how Self-realised souls see it. Meaning, the world is a play between the false and the true. So my views here are part of the play of *Bhagavān* (the Creator). Let the play therefore begin.

Details of my Connection with SES and SSNP

I was a student at SES for 10 years and after that for more than 15 years I was closely associated with the SSNP. It was the leader current at that time, Dr.FCR himself, who sponsored me to join SSNP. My only reason for eventually leaving was because of the realisation that SSNP would never become the equivalent of what I was really seeking; which is a simple, traditional and effective method of Advaita Vedanta teaching, for an individual to realise his/her identity with the Creator of the universe. I retain no adverse thoughts whatsoever about the SES, SSNP or toward any of the people that I met in those places.

² From an audience with Shri Swami Satyananda Maharaj in Vrindavan Nov. 1991

The SSNP was secretive for many decades. Therefore, the only way of joining SSNP was to be sponsored by an established member with a recommendation. I had no one to sponsor me. But my reason for asking to join impressed the leader Dr.FCR, enough for him to sponsored me himself. This indicates that no one could join without a sponsor, as Dr.FCR had to do it to get me in. Dr.FCR wrote to me in a letter on joining, part of which reads:- **"Your previous experience with Advaita Vedanta will be of value to us in our search for Truth."**

Looking at the SSNP website in 2014, it appears to be quite desperate by comparison with those early criteria, with their new all too easy entry and almost open door policy.

"If you would like to attend please feel free just to turn up, it is not necessary to telephone us in advance and there is no charge."

"You are welcome to attend an introductory course in, The Philosophy of the Cosmic Dance, studying Advaita and Mevlevi and other non-dual teachings."

"Non members of the Society are especially welcome and the meetings are found to be of particular help to those who have spent some time investigating the non-dual concepts and wish to test their understanding with others of a like mind."

The people who carefully selected members in the early decades of the SSNP group would most likely turn in their graves if they were to read this. I am certain that Dr.FCR would never have approved opening their doors to all passers-by. This approach is quite contrary to the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition whereby the Self-realised souls never go to the street to preach or recruit followers; which comes from the Bhagavad Gitā Chpt.18 v.67.

"This is never to be spoken by you to one who is devoid of austerities, nor to one who is not devoted, ---"

Readers should take note of how basic principles set up by founder members of philosophy schools can be changed and that this change is often downward - spiritually.

UK Schools' Connection with the Advaita Vedanta Tradition

The connection in India of the SSNP with the Advaita tradition came about indirectly due to Brahmachari Mahesh (Maharishi) going around the world teaching a meditation system which he claimed was from the tradition which Shri Guru Deva represented. Mahesh always had a picture of Shri Guru Deva behind him when he was talking publicly and promoting his own meditation idea. Also he often made statements that

all of it was the tradition and teaching of his master. This was supposed to give credence to a gullible and unknowing public, to claim the support of an authority in India. An authority which his audience did not know.

The use of a powerful authority as a sales technique is very old. Saul of Tarsus used it often in his phrase, "In the name of Jesus Christ", which followed teaching and ideas of his own, not those of Jesus. Also in the UK any producer who has at any one time sold their product to royalty are allowed to use the royal crest on their product with a statement, "By Appointment to Her Majesty the Queen - suppliers of ---". Many people are duped by these sales techniques, despite the quality of the product.

After more than 50 years of Mahesh's claims that he would create world peace through his meditation system, we have more wars, terrorism and organised violence than ever before. So, as we say, "**the proof of the pudding is in the eating**". What Mahesh and the UK schools have misunderstood is that the teaching of Advaita Vedanta and the teachers who teach it, do not come in order to correct the wrongs of the world as a whole. They are not concerned with the natural occurrence of human ignorance, which according to tradition is programmed to occur in regular cycles, where the good side of human nature eventually overcomes the bad side and visa versa. This is *Bhagavān's* (the Creator's) *līlā* or play. World correction through religion is a Western concept through the mechanism now called Eurocentricism.

It was not until 1959 when Brahmachari Mahesh came to the UK that the SSNP and the SES focussed on India and its ancient teachings. The UK schools were interested in the meditation technique promoted by Mahesh and they met him in London to discover more about it. Later when Dr.FCR was in India for the purpose of studying meditation, he had the opportunity to meet HH Shantanand Saraswati; then the current leader of the Advaita tradition in the North of India. It was from Him that he took a meditation method (not from Mahesh) and in later years Dr.FCR had many audiences on Advaita Vedanta teachings.

Misunderstanding

The premise for which Dr.FCR and LM went to India was not fully understood there. Hence, the teaching given was misunderstood by them from the very outset. More about this follows in the next section. However, it is important to point out that after nearly 30 years of connection with HH Shantanand Saraswati, the misunderstandings came to light after several questions were sent to India from SSNP members in the late 1980s, when I was attending meetings there. However, the nature of the

questions were of more interest to Him than their content. He did not send back answers to those questions. Instead He set a test for all members of SSNP. In this He posed several key Advaita Vedanta precepts into question form for SSNP members to state their understanding of these. This was a wise move by His Holiness, since although He had not realised the misunderstanding of Dr.FCR's original premise, He did suspect that something was seriously amiss and wanted to discover what it was. The answers to these questions by all members were collated and sent to India. The leaders of SSNP were brave enough to tell all groups the reply which came from HH Shantanand Saraswati :-

"You have not clearly followed the teaching I have given over many years. You have been looking at it upside-down from the real meanings intended. You should do a thorough re-think of all your current concepts and go back over all the teaching from the beginning, in order to understand it better."

Some members of SSNP left the group after hearing that.

One cause of this "upside-down" thinking is partly due to a fundamental error connected with the meaning of the word "self" as used by Gurdjieff and Ouspensky and that which HH Shantanand Saraswati means by the word in Sanskrit, which is sometimes translated to "Self" in English. Another source of the "upside-down" is that in the West the physical world is seen to direct the mental world; the drive behind Eurocentricism; whereas Advaita Vedanta teaches that the intellectual, mental and spiritual worlds are the cause of the physical world.

The teaching from India received by both SSNP and SES was originally in Sanskrit, or a combination of Hindi with many Advaita Vedanta Sanskrit words. This needed translation into English, as neither Dr.FCR nor LM had sufficient grasp of either Hindi or spoken Sanskrit. This is another important factor behind the misunderstandings which have arisen; since there are many words which cannot be successfully translated.

SECTION TWO

DIFFERENCES IN UK PHILOSOPHY SCHOOLS

Introduction

Where there are schools of thought teaching Advaita Vedanta they need to be examined on the basis of the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition and its traditional method of teaching. With written language having many drawbacks, we cannot avoid some misunderstandings, but I will try to be as clear as possible and of course as fair as can be in the circumstances.

The differences discussed here are a snapshot in time. They relate to personal experience between 1964 and 1990 (when I left SSNP) and information from 21st century published books and internet forums, which I am able to glean in respect of corroboration of these differences, at the time of writing (2014). This mainly relates to the origins and formation of the UK schools and errors in the early decades of their connection with the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition. All things change with time. Earlier errors may have been understood and addressed by the UK schools. But they may have affected how things are now, if they are entrenched into the way the schools' leaders think.

The changes in UK schools in the 21st century may mean the present situation does not tally with what is written here. The historical relevance here is the basis upon which the UK schools formed their understanding of the Advaita Vedanta tradition. This earlier understanding is certainly full of misconceptions. Readers, especially UK school members, need to make a sincere attempt to take a truly investigative stance here and be objective. Others may take note and be forewarned.

The Start of the Enquiry into the Self

In my early 20s I read with alacrity the account given by Ouspensky of the teaching and ideas which he had heard from Gurdjieff. I was thrilled and very interested in the concepts which were put forward. I had never encountered such matters before and was completely taken in by the text in the book³. A similar sense of new discovery comes to many who join these UK schools, the new ideas have an immediate appeal. For many years I seriously believed the concepts which were contained in the "system" as he called it. Later, however, I discovered that the Ouspensky book was not written by a Self-realised person nor was it the result of meeting such a person. Hence it could be very misleading and damaging; spiritually. This is only important for those who seek the True Self.

³ In Search of the Miraculous 1950 : This shows that book knowledge alone can be misleading.

There are many reasons why the "system" of Ouspensky never was anything to do with Advaita Vedanta. Naturally, as with all philosophical subjects there will be common terms and areas of study. But the belief that the Gurdjieff "fragments" were part of the ancient Advaita Vedanta teaching must be completely dismissed. This is the safest approach; the clean slate.

We must go back to the original statements by Ouspensky himself, in his own hand. There in his book he clearly stated that he had come in contact with the ancient tradition in India in at least two forms; those of the followers of Ramakrishna and the *yogis* in India who had discovered *samādhi*. Both are part and parcel of the Advaita Vedanta system in India, but Ouspensky's opinion of these types shows that Advaita Vedanta was **NOT** the "system" he was looking for.

About the Ramakrishna monks he stated:-

"--They were of a slightly sentimental moral-philosophical type with a shade of asceticism, --- but I did not feel they had real knowledge."

About the *yogis* of India he said:-

"--They are based on the creation of trance states, in my eyes this was something of the nature of "spiritualism". I could not trust them; all their achievements were either self-deception or what the Orthodox mystics (in Russia) called 'beauty' or 'allurement'." ⁴

It was Vivekananda who revived interest and promoted the Advaita Vedanta system of Adi Śaṅkara through the Ramakrishna *Maṭhas* which he set up; the Ramakrishna Mission is worldwide. Ramakrishna Paramahansa and his disciple Swami Vivekananda are universally recognised as being two of India's greatest holy men of the 19th century. Hence we must ask, **"Was the above statement by Ouspensky a wise one or not?"** Similarly readers will need to understand that a *yogi* is one who is in union with *Bhagavān* (the Creator), and is not a person who performs physical exercises for money; as do the current Europeans who profess to be experts in *yoga*. Ouspensky was seeing India through European / Russian tinted glasses; unknown to him he suffered from Eurocentricism.

Since those early days in my 20s I have learned to think more clearly about various facts reported by Ouspensky, especially since I have become the disciple of a Self-realised teacher who stays mainly in Vrindavan, UP in India, who never wanted to gather followers. Hence, in order to meet him I needed a letter of recommendation from a man in

⁴ Two quotes from "In Search of the Miraculous" 1950 : by P.D.Ouspensky

London UK, whom He sincerely trusted and had known for more than 40 years at the time I made contact. I was then invited to audience with him.

This teacher's first language is English because he was educated in Kerala south India, where the men in the families all speak English as a first language. This is a very important point here; that there was no need whatsoever for an intermediary in the form of a translator; thus eliminating one important source of misunderstanding. He fully explained all Sanskrit words which he needed to use. All meetings with Him were tape recorded and have been listened to many times in the UK; this is because hearing the teaching over and over again is part of the Advaita Vedanta system of instruction, so as to permanently remove false knowledge and doubt, step by step over a period of time. Ramakrishna Paramahansa often repeated the same teaching to His disciples. Read the biography of his last years called "The Gospel of Ramakrishna."

Missing Essentials

The Ouspensky "system" originally followed by the UK schools did not have a concept of four important subjects:- (1) Three *gunas* of *prakṛti*; (the all powerful qualities of Mother Nature) (2) Knowledge of reincarnation of the human soul; (3) The knowledge of the immutable soul in all human beings; or (4) The concept of *karma* in its aspect of results of actions. In the book⁵ by Ouspensky the word "soul" does not appear. This absence of teaching about the purity and perfection which already exists in the Self of all (item 3 above), if it were the only mistake or missing element, is enough to dismiss any connection between the Ouspensky "system" and Advaita Vedanta. Hence, the absence in the "system" of all four of those subjects mentioned above should show any erudite student of philosophy, clear enough evidence of the two being independent systems of thought. Both may lead to a higher goal in life but they are not the same system; and should not have been mixed up.

On page 40 of the Ouspensky book there is a clear statement where Gurdjieff is reported to have said:-

"Immortality is one of the qualities we ascribe to people without having sufficient understanding of their meaning. Other qualities of this kind are - 'individuality', in the sense of an inner unity, 'a permanent unchangeable I', 'consciousness', and 'will'. All these qualities can belong to man," (he emphasised the word 'can'), "but this certainly does not mean that they do belong to him or belong to each and every one."

⁵ In Search of the Miraculous.

I guess Gurdjieff may have been speaking in Russian. As far as I know we cannot ascertain this. However, there cannot be a great deal of error in the phrase '**a permanent unchangeable I**', or in the word '**consciousness**', when translated. In any case the "system" in the UK and all the "work" proceeded with the absence of the four subjects mentioned above. The "system" was aimed at somehow or other trying to acquire item 3 of those four. This one paragraph, (and there are many, many others in the book giving similar evidence), shows that both Gurdjieff and Ouspensky were not looking at a system related to the inner being (soul) but more likely to do with what Europeans call the subconscious mind.

The four items listed above are the basis for the life of all human beings and they do not need to be acquired, but only to be studied and understood. The big question is, as we may see below, what could these two men have attributed to the word "self" in their much used phrase "self-remembering" around which the "system" was centred? It clearly could not be that which Advaita Vedanta holds as the Self, because their "system" did not have any concept which included this. They were quite learned and intelligent, in the worldly sense. But does this equate to spiritual wisdom? This idea of "self-remembering" was a central plank of the way in which SSNP and subsequently SES approached their work.

Many who read this may have been and may still be, members of these UK schools. Hence, a strong sense of loyalty they may have could act as a barrier. Such sentiments are understandable; they are part of the good side of human nature. Attachment to these sentiments and the people or organisations for whom they are felt, can become a huge obstacle to reading and truly comprehending what is written here. Dr. FCR, who was a wise man, later in life understood the above omissions.

These misconceptions are common to most Europeans when looking into the philosophy of the East. So this paper is an exposé of *ignorant ideas* - not of *people* or *particular schools*. It is however a fact that these ideas do infect the minds of people in such a way that they take over their thoughts, words and actions, thereby impacting on other people whose lives may be affected by trusting and believing in the misguided persons or school. Spiritually ignorant people cannot lead others along the path to Truth, even if some of them have listened to the translated teachings of a Self-realised teacher. They must become free of their own ignorance first (i.e. become Self-realised) before they try to teach others. Otherwise it is only the blind leading the blind.

Let us not forget we are treating this as *Bhagavān's* playtime.

Initial Error of Premise to go to India.

Dr.FCR, for whom I have love and respect, had been following the Ouspensky "system" for about 30 years before he went to India in 1960 / 1961. The search had been on since 1947 to find the missing parts of the "system", which was also called "**fragments of an unknown teaching.**" There was so much talk about "**work on knowledge**" and "**work on being**". Concepts which come directly from Gurdjieff. These do not correlate with the Vedanta subjects of acquisition of knowledge and developing devotion. They may seem similar, but they are not the same thing. Both knowledge and devotion in Vedanta are associated with purification of the *antahkaraṇa*, or inner organ of man.

However, both Dr.FCR and LM⁶ did not go to India to seek a spiritual teacher. Their initial premise was to learn about the missing part of the "system", which they would have called "**work on being**". They already believed in the "system" and they were teachers of it themselves. Later reports bear this out, as on return to the UK they stated that they had found the missing part of the "system"; meditation. There was no chance that they were going to abandon all that they had been following for many decades and start afresh as far as the knowledge was concerned. However it is the clean slate approach which will press the correct buttons in the mind of a true teacher and bring forth the deeper aspects of the Advaita Vedanta teaching. Had they been prepared to forget all the previous teachings they had followed they may have been more open to hearing about Advaita Vedanta. After all, Ouspensky did ask Dr.FCR to abandon the "system" and start afresh. Perhaps they did not realise that HH Shantanand Saraswati was fully aware of their weak motive for coming to India, since they did not kiss His feet and submit themselves to Him totally. Meaning that He would apply the pre-prepared *Śāṅkar-āchārya* system which would suit the spiritually lightweight European understanding of philosophy. Let me explain.

The tradition of the holy men in India had been through the Mogul invasion many centuries before. Prior to the 20th century they had passed through centuries of their country being dominated by the arrogant attitude of the British and other Europeans. It was sure that they had a method of dealing with the spiritual ignorance of the West. The common view with Indian holy men is that generally people from Europe and the USA are not really capable of understanding the philosophy of India, due to so many language and cultural differences; and the mentally closed

⁶ Dr. FCR the leader of SSNP and LM the leader of SES, current at the time I was a member.

nature of Western culture. Hence a formula and guarded approach had been developed long before the UK school leaders set foot in India. This approach however is not always spoken of, it is simply applied in the most polite way. It includes a suitable introductory method of Vedanta.

Error Related to the Word "self"

Much of the enquiry which has developed by UK schools, came about originally through G.I.Gurdjieff starting to teach other people about a subject which he only had part of the information. He attracted P.D.Ouspensky who was interested in a similar enquiry. Both men had spent many years travelling in the Middle East and the Indian sub-continent to uncover a teaching, which might develop Europeans in the area of psychology and other matters of the mind and intellect. Both of these men admitted that they only found fragments of the teaching which they sought. Yet they decided they were in a position to teach others! This approach never was ever, any part of the true tradition of Advaita Vedanta. In that noble tradition, no true seeker would consider teaching another unless he had glimpsed the True Self within his own life first. This is based on the handed down tradition, that all those who are not Self-realised are in ignorance of the true meaning of the philosophy and therefore cannot teach it properly to others. The "Self" mentioned here is the one True Self which is not different in anyone, anywhere or any time. It is not the individual changeable worldly self called *jīva* or *jīva-atman*, which is a more tangible aspect of the True Self (*ātman*), and is contaminated through its attachment to the physical body, overcome with desire, for wealth, fame, pleasure or power.

The method of the UK schools started off with the Gurdjieff idea that **"we need to remember ourselves"**. It was previously made clear that he did not attribute it to mean the True Self of Advaita Vedanta. Neither did he have any concept that there was such a thing as the True Self. The Gurdjieff idea was that the human being has no permanent self (or soul) but his "work" was to build or create a permanent inner centre. How therefore could he have taken **"remembering the self"** to mean the True Self? There is no teaching in Advaita Vedanta whatsoever, of creating a self or a permanent centre. Even so, Ouspensky did not dismiss this aspect of Gurdjieff's teaching. He taught in the UK that the work of the system was about **"remembering ourselves"**. This was implemented by SSNP and SES as various methods of snapping out of daydreams or circling thoughts so that the individual self would realise where s/he was and what s/he was doing in the world. This is not what is meant in

Advaita Vedanta by "**remembering the Self**". HH Shantanand Saraswati confirmed this in His statement to SSNP and SES:-

"The whole thing is that we do not remember ourselves. All our troubles come from not remembering ourselves; only we can't talk about this at the beginning because it is never understood. You will have to reach (Self) realisation before you can understand it."

Never means never. Those ignorant of the True Self cannot know what true "Self remembering" is. How therefore can a school approach this subject as if it *is* known and then teach it to others? The answer comes from the Ouspensky compound mistake. Firstly believing that he had enough knowledge to qualify him to teach others about a very intangible subject. Secondly, it is because there was no "permanent self" in his system, that he used the word "self" to mean that thing which we all can grasp as tangible to some extent - i.e. the *jīva-atman* or the idea of 'myself' which interacts with the world and is sometimes daydreaming or is having thoughts about things which are not present. The methods applied to this SSNP or SES idea of self-remembering were all about focussing in some way more intensely on the material world of the external senses and the actions we carry out in that world. There is no teaching anything like this in Advaita Vedanta. It is in fact quite the opposite. The Advaita Vedanta method is to turn away, for a time, from the material world to the inner world deeper than the mind and intellect. Leaving behind all consideration of the physical world and any attraction to sense objects; and to contemplate the teachings received.

The man who started SES philosophy section, LM, was right in one observation which he made in the early stages of his enquiry into these matters, when he said, "**People heard different things when words were spoken. They changed the sounds into something else.**" What he did not do however, was to apply this observation to his own understanding of the word "self" and the word used in Advaita Vedanta which translates into "Self". How fundamental a mistake was this? Realising this mistake would have been difficult for a man who started off along the lines, "**I realised that there was such a thing as truth and when found it could be taught.**"⁷. Advaita Vedanta does not teach Truth, it only points us in the direction of it. As the Sufi story of the Mulla Nasrudin says:-

Question:- "Mulla, what is Truth?"

Answer:- "Something about which I have never spoken, nor shall I."

⁷ Quotes taken from the biography of LM "The Power Within" by Dorine Tolley ISBN 9781 4392 1030 7

Each individual needs to find Truth for themselves. Anyone who understood this, his/her whole life would be to get Self-realisation for him/herself. After which if others were to benefit from that it would not be of any concern to him/her at all. Read the account of LM's last year or so ⁸ and decide for yourself if he had found Self-realisation through all that he did over so many years.

The Difference Related to Obtaining Self-realisation

Springing from the above error, UK schools have treated the acquisition of Self-realisation much along the lines of obtaining a Masters Degree from a university; viz. although not many may get it, if you are prepared to try hard and put in the necessary work, then you will get there eventually if you follow our course and apply your own effort.

Why do I say "springing from" ? If we look carefully at this error we will see that UK schools have redefined the Advaita Vedanta term "Self" in accordance with LM's own observation, **"They changed the sounds into something else."** This followed from Ouspensky's error, where he applied "self" to mean the worldly self, since there was no soul or permanent self in his system. All UK schools following his line of work would already have this surface and tangible meaning to the word "self" embedded within their psychology. Hence, when going to India to discuss matters related to the "self" their questions and view of the answers would relate to different meanings of the word "self".

When returning to London to pass on the teaching, they continue to instruct their students to **"Watch the working surface."** or **"Stop circling thoughts and pay attention."** All such instructions aimed at bringing this surface and impermanent *jīva-atman* more strongly into view. Self-realisation in their way is to be in a permanent state of always paying 100% attention to the physical world, or always being fully aware during the daytime hours. In other words it is aimed at enhancing the experience in the physical world. This may not be what they intend, but it is the most likely outcome which their members will experience. Advaita Vedanta, however is the opposite of this. Also in Advaita Vedanta there is no concept of mass production of Self-realised people. Here we may be getting closer to the statement "upside-down".

Apart from Gurdjieff's strange idea of what knowledge consisted, there was one aspect of his words which was very close to the mark when discussing the dissemination of knowledge:-

⁸ Chapters 17 & 18 of The Power Within by Dorine Tolley ISBN 9781 4392 1030 7

" -- Taken in a large quantity in a given place, that is by one man, let us say, or by a small group of men, it produces very good results; taken in a small quantity (that is, by every one of a large number of people), it gives no results at all; or it may give even negative results, contrary to those expected. " ⁹

It is a pity that the leaders of the UK schools did not observe this principle in the way they approached Self-knowledge.

Assuming Indian Support for UK School Methods

The leaders of UK schools were fortunate in being accepted in the *āśram* of HH Shantanand Saraswati. Like many Europeans seeking teachers in India around that time, they believed that because He answered their questions, then He supported the way that the UK schools were applying the teaching, which came from the answers He gave. I say "fortunate" because some *Śaṅkarāchāryas* will not meet or answer questions of those who come from Europe or the USA.

There are many organisations in India, called *samāj*, who form groups to study Vedanta. All the Self-realised souls who decide to teach others will happily advise the leaders or members of these groups. Their role as *Śaṅkarāchāryas* is to provide a guiding light to people with any sense of enquiry into the nature of the Self. This does not mean that they agree with what these organisations are teaching or their methods. Rama-krishna Paramahansa often accepted people from various Indian philosophy schools (*samāj*) into His audiences. He advised them but He did not agree with what they were doing. He also stated that people would have to leave such organisations if they wanted to discover the True Self within. The general attitude in India is not to condemn anyone who makes any attempt to study and teach philosophy or religion. Such is the approach of the *Śaṅkarāchāryas* too.

The Error of the Unclean Slate

Another simple principle is not understood by UK schools, which is that His Holiness Shantanand Saraswati is obliged to answer those questions about the Advaita Vedanta system which are put to Him, this is mainly what the appointment to *Śaṅkarāchārya* entails. We should however understand that what is answered is in accordance with the following known and applied approach :-

A very learned man went to a Zen teacher for spiritual instruction.
The Zen teacher was Self-realised, hence he could clearly see that

⁹ From "In Search of the Miraculous" by P.D.Ouspensky. (1950).

the man's mind was already full of ideas that he knew much about the path to realisation already. He offered a cup of tea to the visitor. When pouring the tea for his guest the cup began to overflow, but the master continued to pour. The tea was flowing across the table and onto the floor, but the master continued to pour. The guest could no longer keep silent and burst up with the words, "Can you not see that the cup is full, you cannot get any more into it?" To which the master replied, "Yes I can see. This is the condition of your mind. Come back when you are empty of ideas and I may teach you."

From the above we need to glean two important pieces of information. The first is that when approaching a Self-realised teacher we must be empty of any idea that we already know any aspects of the path whatsoever. Secondly, the words spoken by a teacher to one who is already full of ideas, will not be the same as those words spoken to a true seeker, who has submitted his whole life into the hands of the teacher for instruction; and has come with a clean slate, as it were, to that teacher. It is very important that this principle is understood, as it is the method by which the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition has maintained its own internal integrity for thousands of years. No knowledge is held back when the "clean slate" principle is in operation and the aspirant is a suitably qualified and advanced person.

How is it possible to engage in question and answer with a truly holy man for 30 or more years and both parties to finally realise that the understanding of the teaching has been "upside-down" ? (see HH Shantanand's statement on page 11). The unclean slate is the answer. Is this the reason that the SSNP and the SES have been unable to make a success of their contact with a most wonderful and knowledgeable teacher in India? Have they been to the *Śaṅkarāchārya* with a sack full of ideas from the past, which has affected both what they were taught and their understanding of it?

Belief that UK Schools Have Brought Advaita Vedanta to Europe

When the leaders of the above mentioned schools went to have audience with His Holiness Shantanand Saraswati, they made no secret of the fact that they already had established schools in the UK teaching philosophy. They clearly stated that it was their belief that their schools were already progressing on the path to Self-realisation and they needed both advice and confirmation of this from His Holiness. It is this "**unclean slate**" approach which would have precluded many important aspects of the Advaita Vedanta teaching from being given in the answers.

His Holiness is in the position of knowing that all things are subject to the Will of *Bhagavān* the Creator. Included in this realisation is the knowledge that for a person to become a true seeker of the Self is rare (i.e. it does not happen to people en-mass). Also He knows that it is the grace of *Bhagavān* Himself which would enable the possibility for that true seeker to find a true teacher. With this knowledge in mind He would only give answers which may later attract anyone who hears them, to seek out a competent teacher for themselves as individuals. When a question was asked by UK school leaders to HH Shantanand Saraswati, as to whether a large organisation can have the same relationship with Him as a disciple might have, He replied :-

"No! The disciple relationship is only possible with individuals. Only individuals can establish such relationships with a teacher, and thereby pass on the teaching. Such a relationship cannot be chosen by any particular person. The realised teacher will choose the ones who are suitable. Very, very few find their way to such a relationship."

One man who had been 50 years at SES stated in his book¹⁰ that after 30 years of question and answer :-

"It drew forth a system of knowledge that precisely met the needs of the West at this time, a unique version of the ancient tradition of Advaita Vedanta, not given in that form even to the master's disciples in India."

Since the fact is I attended SES for 10 years and for 15 years after that at SSNP, I am able to say that the established approach to the teaching at SES was no different to that of SSNP in principle. What therefore does the "**upside-down**" statement made by Shantanand Saraswati, mean in relation to the words, "**a unique version of the ancient tradition of Advaita Vedanta**"? Does it mean the UK schools' understanding of it is entirely their own (false) interpretation of the ancient teaching?

The statement in that book comes across as a little bit of an arrogant boast. i.e. "*we have got something others have not got.*" unless I am mistaken about the intention in those words. But there is one matter which cannot be mistaken. The author of that book must be quite clear that he has no way of knowing what the *Śaṅkarāchārya* teaches His own close disciples. I have spent many audiences with His Holiness Shri Swami Satyananda Maharaj, which were hours at a time alone with Him. I know from personal experience that He spoke differently to His close disciples,

¹⁰ In Search of Truth - Brian Hodgkinson - ISBN 978 0 85683 2765.

compared to that which He taught a larger number of people. Readers can judge for themselves whether it is simply guesswork or ignorance for one who is not a disciple to state what a teacher would say to his close disciples.

There is no worse ignorance than the kind which arises from a false perception, that a tradition is known and is being followed, when the reality is the reverse of this and those who have the false belief that they are following the tradition are unaware of their ignorance.

He Who Claims to Know - Knows Nothing

Ouspensky's mistake is repeated in the SSNP and SES, which was that the leaders should have discovered Truth in their own life first, or become accepted as an established disciple of a Self-realised human being, before trying to help others on that same path. It is this method or process that the aspirants of Advaita Vedanta go through in India, before they become suitable as true teachers of the Advaita Vedanta philosophy. Though it is true there are many false teachers in India.

The SSNP leaders asked His Holiness Shantanand Saraswati :-

"Is the main objective of a school to help its leader to become Self-Realised?"

His answer was :-

"Yes! This is so. The school for its own benefit must help the leader so that he can experience himself (be Self-realised). A leader must find this before he can pass it on to anyone else."

These words are confirmation of the tradition mentioned above of not teaching others until Self-realisation had been reached. So the approach by these UK schools is completely upside-down to the approach in India. In India true seekers find a teacher, after some years of instruction they leave the teacher and go through a personal formula for decades which will include solitude. If they become Self-realised they may gather followers who are attracted to their holy personality and teaching. Where no suitable seekers are around the role of teacher does not arise. Many Self-realised souls never teach others.

The UK upside-down approach seems to believe in the opposite to this Indian scenario. The UK school starts with being far away from the true path and tries to create realised souls within a misguided method. This can only lead to them going further and further from the truth. Seeking advice from a realised soul who is distant in language, culture and tradition from the place where the new school is struggling, is not a suitable replacement for the traditional Indian model of achieving Self-

realisation. Also teaching Advaita Vedanta en-mass will only produce ignorance of what it is.

In the words of a living spiritual leader in India,

"Only one who is in the light can lead others into the light, those who are in darkness can only lead others into darkness." ¹¹

The Idea of the Fourth Way

In his many travels around the Middle East Gurdjieff met up with a wide range of spiritual people and systems. Resulting from this he decided that there were three main types who distanced themselves from human society in one way or another. He called these the monk, the *yogi* and the fakir. It seems he did not meet up with many who sought the same goal as these three but did not separate themselves from human society. Hence he believed this fourth type was a rarity. But it may have been that because they had learned to follow a spiritual life in conjunction with a normal life that they were also accustomed to keep the spiritual side of their life from the eyes of others in society. He called the fourth type as members of what he designated "The Fourth Way."

This concept comes from Gurdjieff's own invention. It maybe that someone somewhere had a notion of a number of ways in which seekers can approach their spiritual goal. He applied the number four to the person who lives within a society and perhaps raises a family.

The mistake by UK schools was firstly to believe in the Fourth Way idea invented by Gurdjieff and secondly assuming that his idea is the same as the Indian concept of the householder way known there as the *gr̥hastha*. From this they have assumed they can teach Advaita Vedanta as a method for Self-realisation to anyone who is a householder, and who may never have been a true seeker of the Self within, in their previous embodiment. In India the term *gr̥hastha* used in Advaita Vedanta relates to a seeker of Truth, not necessarily an ordinary householder.

There is no mention of the concept of a "fourth way" in any of the Advaita Vedanta scriptures in connection with the way of the householder; *gr̥hastha*. Teaching the various aspects of the philosophy is not a mistake. Creating the impression that all people coming to their schools have the chance of Self-realisation, is the mistake. The true way of the householder is as described fully in the Preliminaries in the aforementioned book (ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0.). It was also the way used by the Mevlevi (Pythagorean) Sufis for more than 700 years in the transmission of the Pythagorean Sufi way in Turkey.

¹¹ Shri Swami Satyananda Maharaj.

Idea That There is no Need to Find a Teacher

The UK schools have all steered their followers away from the idea that Truth can only be found at the feet of an accomplished teacher; by giving the impression from day one that the school is that accomplished teacher. When later on members may begin to shift their idea that the school is not all that it "*said on the tin*", they are further dissuaded from looking outside the school environment by indicating that the catalogue of questions and answers between school leaders and HH Shantanand Saraswati are the equivalent of the need to find a teacher; this *schmacks* of Eurocentricism. Thus individuals are misled into believing that the school is sufficient for the entire journey to Truth in the life of the individual. Because of this the school is not able to do what true teachers do. This would entail giving specific individual direction over a period of time until the teacher is sure the disciple is on the correct track. Then, not allowing the disciple to remain attached to the teacher when he is ready to stand on his own feet and seek his own individual path. He then leaves the teacher fully equipped to go the whole way along the path to Self-realisation. After this he may need long periods of solitude. Instead the UK schools seem to expect their members to become more and more attached and involved with the school and to remain there for life. This maybe good for the school but it cannot lead to liberation; only bondage.

In addition to this they have invented the idea that the smallest unit in spiritual work is a group of people. This is a simple method for stamping out any complaints, dissent or individuality in understanding the teaching; a form of Eurocentricism. This concept is not acceptable in Advaita Vedanta, wherein each individual is recognised as needing different spiritual guidance in accordance with previous personal progress.

Asking for Money in Exchange for Meditation or Teaching

At the time I was at SES they would introduce students to the system of meditation which came from HH Shantanand Saraswati (not the same as Mahesh's system). Students were made to feel obliged to pay about 2% of their annual income at the time of receiving the meditation method.

Meditation in the Advaita Vedanta tradition is called *upadeśa* or initiation. It can include the use of a specific sound "*mantra*", used for the purpose of training the mind to become still and focussed. In the Advaita Vedanta tradition it is never sold for money.

About this subject His Holiness Swarupananda Saraswati, *Śaṅkarāchārya* of Dvaraka, West India, said:-

"This is a principle. Hear a quotation from Goswami Tulsidas: '**The guru who charges or takes money from his disciples in return for initiation, steals disciples property and goes to damnable hell.**' For that reason His Divinity Shri Guru Deva used to give '**upadeśa**' (initiation) without any fees. He used to say, '**If I accept any gift from the disciple (or fees), then his sins are transmitted to me.**' In India, **dharma, yoga**, knowledge, specialised knowledge can never be sold for money. That is priceless. Anyone who puts a price on it, insults it. So, a **mantra** is also never given for money. Knowledge cannot be sold for money. Therefore, the process that is being employed for the sake of making money, is entirely against the canons of Indian culture and civilization. Where money is involved that becomes a business. I am telling you what is good for you without any vested interest. This is the rule followed here."

Never one rupee was asked of me or any member of my family who came to Vrindavan with me. Swami Satyananda made it clear there was no question of payment whatsoever for being with him and accepting food and accommodation from him. The leaders of the UK schools have not been given authority by HH Shantanand Saraswati to charge for teaching meditation. They took this idea from Brahmachari Mahesh (Maharishi), who knew the principle of no payment well enough. When he was first in the USA he trusted implicitly that all would be provided without the need to ask for money. So he never asked for money, and **Bhagavān** provided everything that was needed.

It was the Americans, who cannot conceive of a thing of value being given away, that gradually corrupted the thinking of Brahmachari Mahesh. Had he been a Self-realised soul who had been given the traditional teaching of the **Brahmin** family tradition, he would not have been at the slightest risk of deviation. However, it is recorded and known fact that Brahmachari Mahesh did not come from a **Brahmin** family and that he never took **samnyas** from any Self-realised teacher in India. This is the reason he slowly drifted further and further from the correct track, under the powerful influence of the desires for wealth, power, fame and pleasure, which beset the whole world in this age. Brahmachari Mahesh's example at the time the UK schools met him, was not true to the Advaita Vedanta tradition. However, due to his amazing charisma the school leaders were at first taken in. Later I know they had doubts. But they were unable to place these doubts into a proper and respectable framework due to lack of information of Brahmachari Mahesh's background

and motives. Also they were not aware of the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition quoted above. Self-realisation can come by luck or by Grace to a person, as it may have done to Brahmachari Mahesh from prolonged close contact with Shri Guru Deva followed by solitude. But if the background and foundation of the person is not strong and traditionally based then the worldly life may cause deviation or non-traditional decisions to be made.

Teaching Meditation and Advaita Vedanta to Children

Some UK schools believe that children need to be taught philosophy and meditation before they are old enough to value it. Also before they are of the proper age of consent to be able agree that it is what they want or need in their lives. This is indoctrination not education.

Children under 8 years of age trust implicitly all that the adults in their lives give them as knowledge and an example to follow. Hence children of cigarette smokers are likely also to smoke; children of bank robbers or burglars are also likely to steal without thinking it is wrong. They are not equipped with the necessary development of their psyche until they have been 100 lunar cycles free from their mother's womb. Hence they will nearly always defend vigorously any part of their lives which has been established before that age. At 8 years of age they would have developed independent thinking, but it will grow mainly on the basis which has been given to them in their earlier years. If they have been given a false understanding of the Advaita Vedanta tradition as described in the text above, prior to the age of 8, then they may never be able to free themselves of such misconceptions. In the ancient Indian tradition a child was not sent to spend time with a *guru* until they were 9 years old. Prior to that they were only taught the good principles of *dharma* - a truthful and correct moral way of life. No deeper concepts of philosophy were taught to them before they were 9 years of age.

Therefore it is recognised in India that there is no purpose in engaging the mind of a child in matters of a spiritual nature until they are psychologically able to evaluate those things as an independent thinker. This shows that the ancient Indian system is based on the natural laws (or numbers) related to human life. Children may remain physically dependent on their parents, but from 8 upwards they are psychologically fully independent beings. Not fully mature, but fully independent, there is a difference between the two aspects.

To force children to take part in spiritual subjects at an early age, risks their rejection of these things later in life; due to getting the underlying feeling that, "**I did not choose these things for myself.**" Surely to any

intelligent person or caring parent this would be a counter-productive strategy to implement.

The children's schools, where the ideas of Advaita Vedanta were taught, started by SES have, proved that the above is true. The internet forum started up by disaffected people who had been sent there as children, shows clearly how much suffering was caused by being forced by the SES tutors. There would have been no problem in these teachers passing on in their own family environment, any true value which they had found in the philosophy. Also they would have been better to have simply been a good example to their children. All children must be allowed to chose individually the spiritual path which they wish to follow, or none. In India it was once common that four brothers may each chose to follow different sects. All true ways are paths to the final supreme goal of life - this was always the traditional view of Indian parents.

Hence to teach young children in the way of SES, does not have the authority or blessing of the *Sanatana Dharma* tradition.

Teaching Meditation as a Stand-alone Subject

It was Brahmachari Mahesh who instigated the concept that meditation could be a standalone subject. This was taught along with his idea that the whole world could utilise a form of meditation which he invented, so as to lead ultimately to world peace. When the leaders of the UK schools met him and took up his idea they were not aware that this concept of a standalone meditation system had never before existed in the *Śaṅkarāchārya* tradition or in Advaita Vedanta scriptures.

Essentially the system of meditation which accompanies the teaching of Advaita Vedanta is a necessary part of the method to bring about control of the mind. If a person who comes to a teacher already has good mental control or has established a connection with the inner peace in their life then they may not immediately need to begin a meditation associated with receiving the teaching. If however the mind is causing them to fail to understand the teaching due to its running away from the point and deviating, then the first stage of meditation is recommended so as to find some mental stillness and to be able to concentrate on the meanings in the scriptures in a more focussed way.

It is for reducing the distraction of mental focus for which the first stage of meditation is designed. This distraction arises from the aspirant not having lead a disciplined life prior to their contact with the teaching. This has allowed the mind to go towards all sense objects without any

control. This has been the habit of many lifetimes. Brahmachari Mahesh's idea that **"by simply meditating people will find peace"** was very misleading. It is true that meditation can bring quick results in finding some degree of mental peace. If the person's life is not regulated by themselves, so that they are less and less attracted and involved with sense objects (i.e. by following a regulated and disciplined life) then the peace so quickly found will be equally quickly lost. This is due to the mind becoming involved and distracted by allowing desires for sense pleasure, wealth or power over others to grip the mental processes. It is only studying and living by the scriptures which may lead a person's life into less and less distraction.

Belief that meditation can create a life of prolonged peace when it is not associated with following a regulated and disciplined life is a fundamental error. Brahmachari Mahesh's statement in relation to the benefit of his meditation system, **"Five minutes in the bank and a full day in the market"**, means what it says. Some peace is gained with a few minutes meditation. Then it is all lost in the worldly market of involvement with sense enjoyments. This may suit many people. But it is not of any value for those who truly seek Self-realisation. Only leading a disciplined life will lead to the inner peace being retained due to less sense enjoyments being sought. The choices of discipline are largely those of the seeker.

There is a Chinese proverb that, **"Large pot is filled with small drops."** But there is an Indian corollary to this, **"Small crack in the pot means it will never fill."**

Conclusions

From the above we have clear evidence that there are a number of factors, which when combined have lead to confusion and dissatisfaction about the way Indian philosophy is being portrayed and taught in the UK and in the countries where these UK schools have directed branches of their organisations. The differences between true Advaita Vedanta and the UK schools are :-

- A. The false connection between the "system" of Gurdjieff and Ouspensky and Advaita Vedanta.
- B. The misunderstanding arising from different meanings applied to the word "self".
- C. The idea that Self-realisation can be taught - and this can be en-mass.
- D. Belief that the teachers in India would support the UK schools methods.

- E. Not appreciating the value of the clean slate approach.
- F. The idea that the whole Advaita Vedanta tradition has been transplanted from India by the UK schools.
- G. A lacking in the need to gain a glimpse of the True Self before directing others to find it.
- H. The idea that the Vedanta householder's way is something called, "The Fourth Way." and can be applied to any householder.
- I. The concept that Advaita Vedanta can lead to knowledge of the Self within, without help from a Self-realised teacher. A kind of do-it-yourself approach.
- J. Asking for money in exchange for a meditation *mantra* or for the teaching.
- K. Teaching philosophy and meditation to children under 8 years of age.
- L. Belief that meditation can be truly beneficial without establishing a systematic and disciplined life.

This is a serious catalogue of errors in understanding. These are not new mistakes, they are common to all cultures and nations, from the beginning of the *Kali-yuga*. This *yuga* has one leg upon which it stands – truthfulness or *satya*. It is fundamental that anyone considering the study of Advaita Vedanta should be 100% honest to themselves and hence to all others.

"This above all: to thine own self be true, And it must follow as the night the day, Thou canst not then be false to any man." Hamlet Act 1. Shakespeare

No value will come to them from their study if they are not truthful. If truthfulness is lost there will be no legs for support of the path towards Truth. This will cause human civil life to disintegrate. All those who promote Advaita Vedanta in the public domain have this responsibility, to set a good example to the human race. If they cannot be truthful then there is no hope for human society.

The UK schools involved in promoting Advaita Vedanta should, as objectively as they can, honestly study the above list and attempt to ensure that any item on that list which may apply to them is effectively rectified. This level of truthfulness includes not being untruthful by the omission of telling what must be told to those who they teach. In addition measures should be put in place to prevent recurrence of any errors discovered in their revue of their activities.

But the main purpose of describing these misconceptions is to stand as a warning to all who seriously wish to follow the teaching of Advaita Vedanta and to gain benefit in their life from so doing. Much evidence to show that most of the above misconceptions are things to avoid, can be found within the teaching in the book -"The Life and Teachings of His Divinity Shri Guru Deva - The Way of the Householder." published in 2014. ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0.

But we must not forget that all this is the playtime of the Creator. Hence we can deduce that the UK and other schools are in some way introducing many souls to the precepts of the Ancient System of Righteousness called *Sanatana Dharma*; albeit not traditionally. It is *Sanatana Dharma* on which Advaita Vedanta is based. It was also known by the prophet Daniel and Jesus; but New Testament evidence shows the Jews and others in Palestine did not understand Jesus when he taught it.

Hence, due the UK schools, many souls may be born in their next life and will wish to take up a serious study of this subject. This paper may be of value to such people - if they are lucky to find it.

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Publications referred to in this paper

The book "The Life and Teachings of His Divinity Shri Guru Deva" ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0 may be purchased direct from the publisher, Saraswati Society email saraswati.soc@btinternet.com or through Amazon UK or in Europe.

This is an essential publication for those who wish to have full knowledge and understanding of the *Sanatana Dharma* and who are ready to live their lives by the teaching it contains.

It is a hand made high quality publication which, when out of stock, may be printed and bound on demand. There is a review of the book on Amazon.

Hodgkinson Brian (2010) : *In Search of Truth* : London : Shephard-Walwyn . - ISBN 978 0 85683 2765

Nikhilananda Swami (1942) : *The Gospel of Shri Ramakrishna (2 Vols)* : Mylapore : Ramakrishna Matha.

Ouspensky P (1964) *In Search of the Miraculous* : London : Routledge & Kegan Paul

Monier Williams (1970) - *Sanskrit -English Dictionary* - OUP. London W1,

Swarupananda, Swami (1903) *Translation of the Bhagavad Gitā* : Calcutta : Advaita Ashrama

Tolley D. (2008) : *The Power Within* : USA : Dorine Tolley ISBN 9781 4392 1030

SANSKRIT WORDS & PRONUNCIATION

Many Sanskrit words have no direct English equivalent, hence they need to be kept in the text and their meanings need to be learned by readers who are keen to learn about Advaita Vedanta philosophy. All important words are in *bold italic* text to identify them.

The system of accents used in this paper are those used by the Monier Williams Sanskrit-English dictionary. I have created two fonts, Sanskrit and an accented Book Antiqua (with wider spacing) for this purpose.

There are eleven letters with accents :- ā ḍ ī ḷ ṅ ṅ ñ ṛ ś ṭ ū these are sounded thus:-

ā long vowel 'a' as in father: ḍ as the letter 'd' in dice :
ī long vowel as 'i' in police: ḷ is not used in this book
ṅ the letter 'n' as in none: ṅ as the compound 'ng' in sing
ñ usually compounded with 'j' as jñ together like 'ny' in the Spanish manyana (mañana)

ṛ compounded with ī as ṛī sounds like the 'ri' in verily
ś as the letter 's' in sure: ṭ as the letter 't' in true (rarely used):
ū long vowel 'u' as in rude (also rarely used).

As can be seen all single accented letters, except two, are represented by single letters in normal English sounds. The exceptions are ṅ described above and ś which must sound like 'sh' in English. Common words like *śāstra* must be sounded like *shaastra* or *upanīśad* like *upanishad*.

Other letter sounds and combinations to be careful of are :-

bh as in **abhor**: **ch** as in **mulch**: **dh** as in **adhere**: **kh** as in **inkhorn**
kś as in **makeshift**: **g** is always as in **get** (not as in **germ**):
gh as in **loghut**: **v** is ½ way between **wet** and **vet**:
a as in **man** (not as in **cat**): **e** as in **hey** (not as in **get**):
i as in **bit** (not as in **dice**): **o** as in **so** (not as in **got**):
u is always as in **usual** (never as in **cut** or **put**):

Other letters and combinations are much the same as in normal English.

GLOSSARY OF SANSKRIT WORDS

Word	Sanskrit	English Rendering
āchārya	आचार्य	Knowing or teaching the teacher, master, a spiritual master who has mastered and realised the truths of a philosophical system and instructs pupils in it.
advaita	अद्वैत	Destitute of duality. Having no duplicate. There is not two. Peerless, sole or unique.
antahkaraṇa	अन्तःकरण	The internal organ. The seat of thought and feeling. The heart, the conscience. Combination of mind, intellect and reason.
āśram	आश्रम	A hermitage, abode of a hermit, the cell of a hermit or retired saints or sages.
ātman	आत्मन्	The Self. Principle of life and sensation. The individual soul.
Bhagavān	भगवान्	He who has many divine qualities, among which is that he knows the past, present and future of beings. The all-pervading non-sectarian Creator.
brahmin	ब्रह्मिन्	A person who has developed, in previous lives, a true understanding of <i>Sanatana Dharma</i> ; Traditionally a class (not caste) within Indian society.
dharma	धर्म	Virtue, morality, righteousness. Customary observance, prescribed conduct, duty.
guru	गुरु	Any venerable person, spiritual parent or preceptor from whom instruction in the scriptures, rituals, prayers and <i>mantras</i> q.v.is received.
guna	गुण	Quality, attribute or property. The three qualities inherent in nature. Building blocks of creation.
gṛhastha	गृहस्थ	A householder seeker. Second stage in social life.
ishvara	ईश्वर	The supreme soul, God, the supreme being. Lord of the Universe.
jīva	जीव	Living existing. The principle of life. Any living being. The sense of existence.
jīvātman	जीवात्मन्	The living or personal or individual soul.
kali yuga	कलियुग	The age of (spiritual) darkness. Current age.
karma	कर्म	Action or doing work. The concept of <i>karma</i> states that the results or consequences of our actions return to us at some time. Hence it also means the accumulated effect of our actions which we will have to deal with at some time. It makes the present life.
līlā	लीला	Play, sport. Divine play. The cosmic play of the Creator.

Word	Sanskrit	English Rendering
mantra	मन्त्र	Instrument of thought, sacred text or speech. Verse of the Veda. Sound given by a <i>guru</i> q.v. for meditation.
matha	मठ	Monastery. School of learning.
maya	मय	Illusion, unreality, deception, fraud, trick. An unreal or illusory image. Magic, phantom, apparition. With <i>prakṛiti</i> q.v. the source of the visible universe. The cosmic illusion. Made of the three <i>gunas</i> q.v.
prakṛti	प्रकृति	The original or natural form or condition of anything. The material world consisting of the three <i>gunas</i> q.v. Mother Nature.
sādhana	साधन	Leading straight to a goal. Guiding well. Means of accomplishment. Set of spiritual practises.
samādhi	समाधि	Intense absorption, accomplishment. The last stage of <i>yoga</i> q.v. Mind at peace.
samāj	समाज्	Assembly; society. Social studies. Co-operative society. Meeting.
samnyāsa	संन्यास	Resignation, abandonment, renunciation of the world.
Sanatana Dharma	सनतन धर्म	The eternal system of righteousness.
satya	सत्य	Truth, the real.
śankaracharya	शङ्कराचार्य	The great sage and exponent of Advaita Vedanta. Any teacher who has been appointed to head one of the four <i>mathas</i> q.v. in India.
upadeśa	उपदेश	Initiation, spiritual instruction.
upaniṣad	उपनिषद्	Sitting down at another's feet to listen to his words. Or setting at rest ignorance, by revealing knowledge of the supreme spirit. Esoteric doctrine, secret doctrine.
yogi	योगि	A contemplative saint, devotee, ascetic. One who seeks union with God. He who follows a path leading to the Divine.
yoga	योग	Joining or harnessing of two into one. A way, manner or method. Teaching and practice of the means by which the human spirit may reach complete union with <i>Ishvara</i> . q.v. Concentration of thought, abstract concentration, meditation. Any spiritual <i>sadhana</i> q.v.